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How Short-Form Video Creates Consumer Value: The Role of Brand Attitude in Driving Purchase Intention on E-Commerce Platform

Nguyen Thi Viet Ha

Faculty of Business Administration, Banking Academy of Vietnam, Hanoi, Vietnam

Nguyen Thi Phuong

Faculty of Business Administration, Banking Academy of Vietnam, Hanoi, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of short-form video marketing on consumer purchase intention in e-commerce, focusing on the mediating role of brand attitude. Grounded in the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research explains how video-based stimuli are transformed into behavioral intentions through internal psychological processes. Data were collected from 226 Shopee users in Vietnam and analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings indicate that scenario experience, perceived usefulness, and interesting content significantly influence brand attitude, which in turn has a strong positive effect on purchase intention. Brand attitude also serves as a key mediating mechanism linking short-form video stimuli to consumer behavioral outcomes. In contrast, user engagement and perceived credibility do not exhibit significant effects in this context. This study contributes to the literature by integrating SOR and TPB to explain short-form video effectiveness in e-commerce and highlights the central role of brand attitude in driving purchase intention. The results provide practical implications for optimizing video-based marketing strategies in emerging digital markets.

KEYWORDS: Short-form video, E-commerce, Purchase intention, Brand attitude, SOR framework, Emerging markets

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of rapid digital transformation, e-commerce has emerged as a dominant channel for consumer transactions, particularly in emerging markets such as Vietnam. Alongside this growth, digital marketing practices have evolved significantly, with businesses increasingly leveraging innovative tools to enhance customer engagement and drive sales performance (Nguyen, 2024). Among these tools, short-form video has become one of the most influential formats, enabling firms to deliver vivid, interactive, and easily consumable content that aligns with contemporary consumer behavior.

Recent industry reports indicate that Vietnam's e-commerce market has experienced substantial growth, with platforms such as Shopee and TikTok Shop integrating video-based features to improve user experience and stimulate purchase behavior. Short-form video content not only facilitates product visualization but also enhances consumers' emotional and cognitive engagement, thereby influencing their decision-making processes. Empirical evidence suggests that video-based marketing significantly impacts purchase intention through factors such as perceived usefulness, entertainment value, and experiential immersion (Meng et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2025).

From a theoretical perspective, the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework provides a robust foundation for understanding how external stimuli - such as short-form video attributes-affect consumer behavior. Specifically, video content characteristics (stimuli) shape internal psychological states (organism), including perceptions, emotions, and attitudes, which subsequently drive behavioral responses such as purchase intention (Shen et al., 2024; Wu & Su, 2025). Complementarily, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) emphasizes the role of attitude as a key determinant of behavioral intention (Ajzen, 1991). Integrating these two frameworks allows for a more comprehensive explanation of how short-form video influences consumer decision-making in digital environments.

In the context of Vietnam, recent studies have confirmed the growing importance of short-form video in shaping consumer behavior. For instance, Ngo et al. (2023) found that short video attributes significantly influence purchase intention among Generation Z through cognitive and experiential factors. Similarly, Thao and Hai (2024) demonstrated that brand attitude plays a mediating role in the relationship between short-form video marketing and purchase intention. Additional evidence from TikTok-based studies also highlights the role of content engagement in driving consumer responses in the Vietnamese market (Nguyen et al., 2023). Furthermore, emerging research on e-commerce psychology suggests that consumers increasingly rely on digital content to evaluate products and reduce perceived risk in online shopping environments (Le, 2024).

Despite these advances, existing research has primarily focused on social media platforms or specific consumer segments, with limited attention given to integrated e-commerce platforms such as Shopee. Moreover, prior studies often emphasize direct relationships between video

attributes and purchase intention, while overlooking the underlying psychological mechanisms that translate external stimuli into behavioral outcomes. In particular, the mediating role of brand attitude within the SOR–TPB integrated framework remains underexplored in emerging market contexts.

To address these gaps, this study examines how short-form video attributes influence purchase intention on the Shopee platform, with a specific focus on the mediating role of brand attitude. Drawing on both SOR and TPB, the study aims to: (1) identify key video attributes affecting consumer attitudes, (2) analyze the mediating role of brand attitude in shaping purchase intention, and (3) provide empirical evidence from Vietnam as an emerging digital market.

By integrating theoretical perspectives and contextual insights, this study contributes to the literature by offering a process-based understanding of how short-form video marketing drives consumer behavior in e-commerce environments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical foundation: Integrating SOR and TPB

The Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) provide complementary perspectives for understanding consumer behavior in digital environments. The SOR framework posits that external environmental stimuli influence individuals' internal psychological states, which subsequently shape behavioral responses (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). In the context of digital marketing, short-form video attributes can be conceptualized as stimuli that trigger cognitive and affective reactions, ultimately leading to behavioral outcomes such as purchase intention (Shen et al., 2024; Wu & Su, 2025).

While SOR emphasizes the process through which environmental cues are transformed into behavioral responses, TPB explains behavioral intention through cognitive determinants, particularly attitude toward the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Attitude reflects individuals' overall evaluation of a behavior or object and is consistently identified as a key predictor of purchase intention across various consumption contexts.

Integrating SOR and TPB enables a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior in e-commerce settings. Specifically, short-form video attributes (stimulus) shape internal evaluations (organism), particularly brand attitude, which subsequently drives purchase intention (response). This integration highlights the mediating role of psychological mechanisms in translating digital stimuli into behavioral outcomes, which remains underexplored in emerging market contexts.

2.2. Research gap

Short-form video marketing as a stimulus in e-commerce

Short-form video has emerged as a dominant content format in digital marketing, particularly within e-commerce platforms. Compared to traditional static content, short videos provide richer sensory experiences, combining visual, auditory, and narrative elements that enhance consumer engagement and information processing. As a result, they play a critical role in influencing consumer perceptions and decision-making.

Recent empirical studies demonstrate that short-form video attributes such as entertainment value, informativeness, and immersive experience significantly influence consumer responses. For instance, Meng et al. (2024) found that video content characteristics directly shape consumer behavior in e-commerce environments by enhancing perceived value and engagement. Similarly, Luo et al. (2025) highlight that short-form video stimuli influence purchase intention through psychological mechanisms such as trust and perceived usefulness.

From the SOR perspective, these video attributes function as external stimuli that trigger both cognitive and emotional responses. Experiential elements, such as scenario-based storytelling, enable consumers to visualize product usage, thereby enhancing perceived relevance and reducing uncertainty. This is particularly important in online shopping contexts, where the lack of physical interaction increases reliance on digital content for product evaluation.

In the Vietnamese context, short-form video marketing has gained significant traction, especially among younger consumers. Ngo et al. (2023) confirm that short video attributes significantly influence purchase intention among Generation Z through experiential and cognitive pathways. Additionally, Nguyen et al. (2023) show that TikTok content plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions and driving engagement, further reinforcing the importance of short-form video as a key marketing stimulus.

Brand attitude as a mediating psychological mechanism

Within the integrated SOR–TPB framework, brand attitude represents a central psychological mechanism that links external stimuli to behavioral outcomes. Brand attitude reflects consumers' overall evaluation of a brand based on their perceptions, emotions, and experiences, and has been widely recognized as a key determinant of purchase intention.

From the TPB perspective, attitude toward a behavior significantly influences the intention to perform that behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In digital marketing contexts, brand attitude captures consumers' evaluative responses to marketing stimuli, including short-form video content. Positive brand attitudes are associated with higher levels of trust, emotional attachment, and purchase intention.

Empirical evidence supports the mediating role of brand attitude in the relationship between marketing stimuli and behavioral outcomes. Thao and Hai (2024) demonstrate that brand attitude significantly mediates the impact of short-form video marketing on purchase intention in Vietnam. Similarly, studies grounded in the SOR framework indicate that internal evaluations, such as attitude and perceived value, play a crucial role in translating external stimuli into behavioral responses (Wu & Su, 2025).

Moreover, recent research emphasizes that experiential and informational value derived from short-form video content significantly enhances brand attitude. Liu and Wang (2023) find that perceived value mediates the relationship between video content characteristics and purchase intention, highlighting the importance of cognitive evaluation in shaping consumer attitudes. These findings suggest that brand attitude serves as a critical mechanism through which short-form video influences consumer behavior in e-commerce settings.

Purchase intention as a behavioral response

Purchase intention represents the likelihood that a consumer will engage in a buying behavior and is widely used as a proxy for actual purchase behavior in marketing research. Within the SOR framework, purchase intention constitutes the final behavioral response resulting from the interaction between external stimuli and internal psychological states.

In the context of e-commerce, purchase intention is influenced by both cognitive and affective factors, including perceived usefulness, trust, and brand attitude. Prior studies have consistently demonstrated that positive evaluations of a brand significantly increase the likelihood of purchase (Sun et al., 2019). Furthermore, digital environments amplify the role of psychological mechanisms, as consumers rely heavily on online information and content to form purchase decisions.

In emerging markets such as Vietnam, the role of digital content in shaping purchase intention is particularly pronounced. Le (2024) highlights that consumers increasingly depend on digital cues, including video content and personalized recommendations, to evaluate products and reduce perceived risk. This underscores the importance of understanding how short-form video influences internal evaluations and, ultimately, purchase intention in e-commerce platforms.

Although prior studies have provided valuable insights into the impact of short-form video marketing on consumer behavior, several gaps remain. First, existing research has largely focused on social media platforms, with limited attention given to integrated e-commerce environments such as Shopee. Second, many studies emphasize direct relationships between video attributes and purchase intention, while overlooking the underlying psychological mechanisms that mediate this relationship.

Third, although brand attitude has been identified as an important determinant of purchase intention, its mediating role within the integrated SOR–TPB framework remains insufficiently explored, particularly in emerging markets. Finally, empirical evidence from Vietnam is still limited, despite the rapid growth of digital commerce and the increasing importance of short-form video in shaping consumer behavior.

To address these gaps, this study proposes a research model that examines the impact of short-form video attributes on purchase intention through the mediating role of brand attitude, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior in e-commerce contexts.

2.3 Research Hypotheses

(1) Interesting content

Interesting content represents a fundamental component of communication value, particularly in digital marketing environments. Drawing on Ducoffe's (1996) advertising value framework, entertainment is a key dimension that enhances the perceived value of advertising by satisfying consumers' need for enjoyment while simultaneously increasing message effectiveness. Entertaining content not only captures attention but also facilitates positive emotional responses, which are essential for shaping favorable evaluations of marketing messages. Subsequent research has consistently demonstrated that entertaining and engaging content enhances consumer involvement, improves message processing, and fosters more positive attitudes toward advertisements (Wang & Sun, 2010; Hussain et al., 2022). When consumers perceive content as interesting, they are more likely to devote cognitive resources to processing information and to develop positive affective responses, which in turn strengthen brand recall and evaluation. Moreover, in digital environments, interesting content encourages sharing behavior and amplifies message diffusion, further reinforcing its impact on consumer perceptions.

In the context of short-form video marketing, the role of interesting content becomes even more critical due to the limited attention span of users. Short videos must capture attention quickly and deliver engaging experiences within a brief timeframe. From the perspective of the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, interesting content functions as an external stimulus that evokes emotional and cognitive reactions, thereby influencing internal psychological states such as brand attitude (Shen et al., 2024). Recent empirical studies provide strong support for this mechanism. Meng et al. (2024) show that creative and engaging video content enhances consumer attention and emotional engagement, leading to more favorable brand perceptions. Similarly, Luo et al. (2025) find that entertainment value significantly contributes to consumers' cognitive and affective responses, which are critical in shaping brand-related evaluations. These findings suggest that interesting content not only attracts attention but also plays a central role in forming positive attitudes toward brands.

In emerging markets such as Vietnam, the importance of interesting content is further reinforced. Ngo et al. (2023) demonstrate that entertaining short video content significantly influences consumer perceptions and purchase-related outcomes, highlighting its role in shaping evaluative responses in digital commerce environments. Based on the above arguments, it can be inferred that interesting content enhances both emotional engagement and cognitive evaluation, thereby positively influencing brand attitude.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H1: *Interesting content positively impacts consumer brand attitude.*

(2) Scenario experience

Scenario experience in short-form video marketing refers to the extent to which content enables consumers to visualize and mentally simulate real-life product usage situations. By embedding products within relatable and context-rich narratives, short videos create a virtual consumption environment in which consumers can imagine how a product fits into their daily lives. From a communication perspective, scenario-based content enhances information processing by presenting fragmented yet personalized messages in meaningful contexts. This allows consumers not only to understand product attributes more effectively but also to construct individualized consumption experiences during their interaction with the content (Liu et al., 2019). In addition, integrating scripted scenarios into video content can evoke strong emotional responses, as consumers tend to empathize more with messages that reflect their personal needs and real-life situations (Kim & Jang, 2014).

Within the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, scenario experience functions as a key experiential stimulus that enhances immersion and facilitates both cognitive and affective processing. By enabling mental simulation and role-playing, scenario-based videos reduce uncertainty, increase perceived relevance, and strengthen emotional engagement, thereby influencing internal psychological states such as brand attitude (Wu & Su, 2025).

Recent empirical studies provide strong support for this mechanism. Meng et al. (2024) demonstrate that immersive and scenario-based video content significantly enhances consumers' perceptions and emotional responses, leading to more favorable brand evaluations. In emerging markets such as Vietnam, where consumers rely heavily on digital content due to limited physical interaction, scenario experience plays a particularly important role in product evaluation. Ngo et al. (2023) confirm that experiential elements in short-form video significantly influence consumer responses by enhancing both perceived usefulness and emotional engagement. Taken together, these findings suggest that scenario experience not only improves consumers' understanding of products but also strengthens emotional attachment and evaluative responses toward brands.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H2: *Experience a scenario that positively impacts consumer brand attitude.*

(3) User participation interaction

User participation interaction refers to the degree to which consumers actively participate in interacting with digital content through behaviors such as searching, commenting, sharing, and providing feedback. In the context of short-form video marketing, consumers are no longer passive recipients of information but active participants in content consumption and dissemination, contributing to a dynamic and multi-directional communication environment.

From a communication perspective, engagement behaviors enhance information exchange and personalization, allowing consumers to interact with brands and other users in ways that enrich their consumption experience (Liu et al., 2019). In the new media landscape, this shift toward participatory communication empowers consumers to co-create and distribute content, thereby strengthening relational ties and fostering a sense of involvement with brands (McQuail, 2010). Such active participation can enhance familiarity, trust, and emotional connection, which are important antecedents of favorable brand evaluations.

Within the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, interactive features embedded in short-form video content function as stimuli that encourage consumer participation and increase involvement. Higher levels of engagement are expected to enhance internal psychological states, particularly brand attitude, by fostering a sense of connection and co-creation with the brand.

However, recent studies suggest that the effectiveness of engagement may vary depending on the nature of the content and platform. In short-form video environments characterized by rapid and experience-driven consumption, engagement behaviors may not always translate into deeper cognitive evaluation or long-term attitude formation (Luo et al., 2025). Nevertheless, empirical evidence indicates that engagement remains an important factor in shaping consumer perceptions and brand-related responses, particularly in interactive digital contexts (Nguyen et al., 2023). Taken together, these arguments suggest that user engagement can enhance consumers' involvement and relational connection with brands, thereby positively influencing brand attitude.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H3: *User Participation Interaction positively impacts consumer brand attitude.*

(4) Perceived credibility

Perceived credibility refers to the extent to which consumers believe that the information presented in short-form video content is accurate, trustworthy, and reliable. In online environments characterized by high levels of information asymmetry, credibility plays a critical role in shaping consumer evaluations and reducing perceived risk.

From a communication perspective, credible information enhances message persuasiveness and facilitates the formation of favorable attitudes toward products and brands (Mir & Zaheer, 2012). Conversely, information perceived as unreliable or misleading can undermine trust and negatively influence consumer perceptions and behavioral intentions (Yüksel, 2016). In digital commerce contexts, consumers often rely on multiple information sources to verify content and minimize uncertainty during decision-making processes (Goldsmith & Horowitz, 2006). As such, content that is perceived as transparent, authentic, and reflective of real experiences is more likely to generate positive evaluative responses.

Within the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, perceived credibility functions as a cognitive stimulus that shapes internal psychological states, particularly trust and brand evaluation. When consumers perceive short-form video content as credible, they are more likely to develop confidence in the information presented, which in turn enhances favorable attitudes toward the brand (Luo et al., 2025).

Empirical studies consistently support the importance of credibility in digital environments. Sun et al. (2019) demonstrate that information credibility significantly influences consumer attitudes and purchase-related behaviors in social commerce contexts. Moreover, authentic signals—such as user-generated content and realistic product demonstrations—can strengthen trust and improve brand perception. In emerging markets such as Vietnam, where consumers increasingly depend on digital information to evaluate products, credibility plays an even more critical role in shaping attitudes and reducing perceived risk (Le, 2024). Taken together, these arguments suggest that perceived credibility enhances consumers' trust and cognitive evaluation, thereby positively influencing brand attitude.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H4: *Perceived credibility has a positive impact on attitudes towards brands.*

(5) Perceived usefulness

Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which consumers believe that short-form video content provides valuable and helpful information for making purchase decisions. In digital environments, where consumers rely heavily on online content to evaluate products, usefulness plays a central role in shaping cognitive evaluations and reducing perceived uncertainty.

Drawing on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), perceived usefulness is defined as the degree to which individuals believe that using a system enhances their decision-making effectiveness (Davis, 1989). In online commerce contexts, this concept extends to the belief that digital content improves the efficiency of information search and product evaluation (Pavlou & Fygenson, 2006). When consumers perceive content as useful, they are more likely to process information more effectively and form favorable evaluations of the associated product or brand (Mir & Rehman, 2013).

Within the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, perceived usefulness functions as a cognitive stimulus that enhances perceived value and supports decision-making processes. Short-form videos that provide clear, concise, and relevant information allow consumers to better understand product features, reduce perceived risk, and increase confidence in their purchase decisions. As a result, consumers are more likely to develop positive internal evaluations, particularly toward the brand.

Empirical evidence further supports this mechanism. Liu and Wang (2023) demonstrate that perceived usefulness significantly contributes to consumers’ cognitive evaluation and plays a mediating role in shaping purchase intention. Similarly, Meng et al. (2024) show that informative video content enhances consumer perceptions and behavioral outcomes in e-commerce environments. In emerging markets such as Vietnam, where consumers increasingly depend on digital content for product assessment, perceived usefulness becomes even more critical in influencing attitudes and decision-making processes (Ngo et al., 2023). Taken together, these findings suggest that perceived usefulness enhances consumers’ cognitive evaluation and decision confidence, thereby positively influencing brand attitude.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H5: *Perceived usefulness positively impacts consumer brand attitude.*

(6) Consumer Brand Attitude

Brand attitude represents consumers’ overall evaluation of a brand, formed through their perceptions, emotions, and prior experiences. As a relatively stable psychological construct, brand attitude reflects not only consumers’ current feelings but also their long-term evaluative judgments, which play a critical role in guiding future behavior (Spears & Singh, 2004).

Within the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), attitude is identified as a key determinant of behavioral intention, as it captures individuals’ favorable or unfavorable evaluations of performing a given behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In consumption contexts, brand attitude reflects the extent to which consumers develop positive or negative perceptions toward a brand based on the information and experiences they have accumulated. Positive attitudes are associated with greater trust, emotional attachment, and perceived value, which in turn increase the likelihood of purchase decisions.

From the perspective of the Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework, brand attitude functions as a central internal psychological state (organism) that mediates the relationship between external stimuli (e.g., short-form video attributes) and behavioral responses (purchase intention). Consumers who develop favorable attitudes toward a brand are more likely to translate these evaluations into concrete purchase intentions.

Empirical evidence consistently supports the strong influence of brand attitude on purchase intention across various digital contexts. Sun et al. (2019) demonstrate that positive evaluations of brands significantly increase consumers’ willingness to purchase in social commerce environments. Similarly, Thao and Hai (2024) confirm that brand attitude plays a crucial role in driving purchase intention in short-form video marketing contexts in Vietnam. These findings highlight that, regardless of the type of digital stimulus, the formation of positive brand attitudes is a key mechanism through which consumer behavior is shaped. Taken together, these arguments suggest that favorable brand attitudes significantly enhance consumers’ likelihood of forming purchase intentions.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H6: *Consumer brand attitude positively impact product purchase intentions*

Research model

Independent Variables (Stimuli)

Nội dung thú vị (IC) → Interesting Content (IC)

Trải nghiệm kịch bản (SE) → Scenario Experience (SE)

Tương tác tham gia của người dùng (UPI) → User Participation Interaction (UPI)

Độ tin cậy được cảm nhận (PC) → Perceived Credibility (PC)

Sự hữu ích được cảm nhận (PU) → Perceived Usefulness (PU)

Figure 1. Conceptual model illustrating the effects of short-form video attributes on purchase intention through brand attitude.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

This study adopts a quantitative research design to examine the relationships between short-form video attributes and purchase intention in an e-commerce context. Drawing on the integrated Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the study aims to test both direct and indirect effects among the proposed constructs.

A survey-based approach was employed to collect primary data from consumers who have experience with short-form video content on the Shopee platform. The use of a structured questionnaire enables the measurement of latent constructs and supports statistical analysis using structural equation modeling.

3.2. Sample and data collection

The target population of this study consists of consumers who have experience viewing product-related short videos on the Shopee e-commerce platform in Vietnam. A non-probability sampling method, specifically convenience sampling, was employed due to accessibility and time constraints.

Data were collected through an online survey distributed via social media platforms and e-commerce communities. The data collection process was conducted in two stages. First, a pilot study involving 49 respondents was carried out to assess the clarity and reliability of the measurement items. Based on feedback, minor adjustments were made to improve the questionnaire.

In the main survey, a total of 240 responses were collected, of which 226 were deemed valid after data screening, representing a usable response rate of 94.16%. This sample size satisfies the minimum requirements for Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), which recommends a minimum of 5–10 observations per indicator (Hair et al., 2010).

The demographic profile of respondents indicates that the majority belong to the 18–34 age group, reflecting a population segment that is highly active in digital environments and frequently engages with short-form video content.

3.3. Measurement scales

All constructs in this study were measured using multi-item scales adapted from prior validated studies to ensure content validity. A five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was employed.

The measurement items for each construct are as follows: Interesting Content (IC), Scenario Experience (SE), User Participation Interaction (UPI), and Consumer Brand Attitude (CBA): adapted from studies on short video marketing and its influence on consumer attitudes (Liu et al., 2019; Thao & Hai, 2024). Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Credibility (PC): adapted from research on factors influencing purchase intention in online video contexts (Yüksel, 2016; Thao & Hai, 2024). Purchase Intention (PI): adapted from prior studies examining consumer purchase intention in short video platforms (Hewei, 2022; Thao & Hai, 2024). All measurement items were translated into Vietnamese and back-translated into English to ensure linguistic equivalence.

3.4. Data analysis method

The study employs Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS software to analyze the data. PLS-SEM is appropriate for this study due to its suitability for complex models, prediction-oriented research, and its ability to handle non-normal data distributions (Hair et al., 2021).

The analysis follows a two-step approach: First, the measurement model is assessed to evaluate reliability and validity. Internal consistency reliability is examined using Cronbach’s alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), with threshold values above 0.70. Convergent validity is assessed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a minimum threshold of 0.50. Discriminant validity is evaluated using the Fornell–Larcker criterion. Second, the structural model is assessed to test the proposed hypotheses. Path coefficients (β), t-values, and p-values are obtained through bootstrapping procedures with 5,000 resamples. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to evaluate the explanatory power of the model, while effect size (f^2) is used to assess the relative impact of each predictor. Additionally, multicollinearity is assessed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with values below 5 indicating no significant collinearity issues (Hair et al., 2020).

To address potential common method bias (CMB), Harman’s single-factor test was conducted. The results indicate that no single factor accounts for the majority of the variance, suggesting that common method bias is not a serious concern in this study.

IV. RESULTS

A. Describe statistics of demographics

The official research sample consists of 226 research samples, meeting the sample size requirements for quantitative analyses. The demographic characteristics of the participants including gender, age, and frequency of purchases through shopee videos are compiled and presented according to the table below:

Table I: Summary of Research Sample Information

Statistics	Content	Amount	Ratio
Gender	Male	96	42,5%
	Female	130	57,8%
Year of birth	Age < 18	1	0,4%
	Age 18-24	128	56,5%

	Age 25-34	71	33,9%
	Age 35-49	21	9,2%
	Age >= 50	0	0%
Have you ever watched product content through Shopee Video?	Ever	174	77%
	Never before	52	23%
Total Survey Sample		226	100%

Source: Self-synthesized author

The statistical table describing the research sample shows the survey participants. In terms of gender, the proportion of women dominated with 57.5% corresponding to 130 people, while men accounted for 42.5%. In terms of age, the age group of 18 - 24 accounted for the largest proportion with 56.5%, followed by the group of 25 - 34 years old with 71 people equivalent to 33.9%; the age group of 35 - 49 accounted for 9.2%; the other two groups were under 18 years old and over 50 years old accounting for a negligible proportion of 0.4% and 0% respectively.

The sample of the study focused mainly on the 18–34 age group, showing that the survey subjects were mostly young people, with a high level of access to technology and digital platforms. This is also a group of users who regularly consume short video content and tend to shop actively online, thus being in line with the context of research on the impact of short videos on purchase intentions on e-commerce platforms. In addition, the predominant percentage of women also reflects the characteristics of a group of consumers who are often more interested in product content and tend to participate in online shopping higher in some categories.

Of the 240 surveyed people, 94.16% have used Shopee (226 people), only 5.84% have not used it (14 people), showing that Shopee is a popular e-commerce platform and the research sample is highly reliable. Regarding the behavior of accessing product content through short videos on Shopee, 77% (174 people) have watched Shopee Video, 23% have not watched it, which confirms that video has become an effective sales tool and reflects the trend of users switching from static content to dynamic content.

4.2. Measurement model assessment

Assessment of Reliability and Validity of the Scale:

The study used data analysis techniques to evaluate the reliability of the scales, with the results detailed in Table 2. To evaluate the reliability of the scale and the value of the model, the study conducted testing through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). According to Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), Black et al. (2005) and Hair et al. (2017), scales are considered reliable when the Cronbach's Alpha value and the aggregate reliability (rho_c) are greater than 0.7.

The results showed that all variables met this criterion. In which, "Interesting Content" 0.918 and "User Participation Interaction" 0.895 were the variables with the highest Cronbach's alpha index. All variables achieved a composite confidence CR of over 0.85; the highest was "Interesting Content" with 0.942; followed by "User Participation Interaction" with 0.927. This result showed that the variables in the model achieved high confidence, reflected well the relationship between the observed variable and the latent variable, and were eligible for further analysis.

In addition, the study also conducted testing of criteria such as structural reliability, convergence values, and distinctiveness according to recognized guidelines (Hair et al., 2019). The reliability of the indicators was confirmed when the exogenous load coefficient of each observed variable exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2019). In addition, the multilinear phenomenon was evaluated through the variance amplification (VIF) coefficient in the internal model (Ringle et al., 2017). The results of the analysis showed that all VIF values were lower than 5.0, thereby confirming that the model did not have multi-community problems (Hair et al., 2020).

Table II. The results of scale test

Construct	Items	Number of Observed Variables	Outer loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE (Average Variance Extracted)	VIF (variance inflation factor)
Interesting Content	IC	4	0,896	0,918	0,942	0,804	3,472
Scenario Experience	SE	4	0,859	0,881	0,918	0,738	3,890
User Participation Interaction	UPI	4	0,872	0,895	0,927	0,760	4,859
Perceived Credibility	PC	4	0,830	0,849	0,899	0,691	2,836

Perceived Usefulness	PU	4	0,870	0,893	0,926	0,759	3,570
Consumer Brand Attitude	CBA	4	0,837	0,858	0,905	0,704	1,000
Purchase Intention	PI	3	0,861	0,827	0,897	0,744	

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS software

Convergence Validity

To assess the convergence validity of the scales, the study used the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) index. According to Hock and Ringle (2010) as well as Hair et al. (2019), a scale is considered valid convergence when the AVE value reaches or exceeds 0.5. In this analysis, the results showed that all the study variables exceeded the standard threshold, with AVE values ranging from 0.691 to 0.804. These results show that the observational variables used in the study are capable of clearly and fully explaining the corresponding potential variables, thereby strengthening the reliability of the research model. As such, it can be asserted that the scales have shown good convergence validity and ensure a solid foundation for further analyses.

Table III. Reliability and Discriminant Validity Correlation Matrix

	CBA	IC	PC	PI	PU	SE	UPI
CBA	0,839						
IC	0,766	0,897					
PC	0,695	0,716	0,831				
PI	0,836	0,720	0,641	0,863			
PU	0,766	0,757	0,747	0,728	0,871		
SE	0,773	0,786	0,721	0,749	0,715	0,859	
UPI	0,768	0,784	0,748	0,736	0,809	0,828	0,872

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS software

Discriminant validity

The discriminatory validity of the latent variables was evaluated based on the Fornell-Larcker index, where the square root of the AVE of each variable was compared to the correlation coefficient between that variable and the other latent variables. The results showed that the square root of the AVE of each variable was greater than its highest correlation with any other variable, demonstrating that the latent variables were clearly distinguishable and not conceptually overlapped. The data presented in Table 3 also support this claim, as the square root values of the AVE of all observed variables exceeded their correlation values with the other latent variables.

In the PLS-SEM model, the aggregate reliability is used as an alternative to the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, as recommended by Sarstedt et al. (2022). The results showed that all aggregate confidence values exceeded the threshold of 0.7, which is in line with the standard of Bagozzi & Yi (1988), indicating that the measurement structures have high internal consistency. In addition, all variables met the normalized load factor according to the recommended thresholds of Fornell and Larcker (1981), demonstrating that each variable makes a meaningful contribution to the respective structure. Overall, these results confirm that the scales in the study are both convergent and well distinguished, while ensuring high reliability, providing a solid foundation for further analysis.

C. Evaluation of the structural model

Results for the proposed hypothesis

Table IV. Path Coefficients of The Concept Framework

Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	Estimates	Standard deviation	T Statistics	P Values	F square	Results
H1	IC=> CBA	0,215	0,082	2,643	0,008	0,046	Accept
H2	SE => CBA	0,287	0,080	3,606	0,000	0,073	Accept
H3	UPI => CBA	0,091	0,085	1,063	0,288	0,006	Refute
H4	PC=> CBA	0,054	0,093	0,576	0,565	0,004	Refute
H5	PU => CBA	0,284	0,075	3,770	0,000	0,078	Accept
H6	CBA => PI	0,836	0,027	31,394	0,000	2,315	Accept

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS software

Based on the structural model assessment, the results indicate that four hypothesized relationships are statistically significant at the 5% level ($p \leq 0.05$). Specifically, interesting content (IC), scenario experience (SE), and perceived usefulness (PU) have significant positive effects on consumer brand attitude (CBA), while consumer brand attitude significantly influences purchase intention (PI). In contrast, the relationships involving user participation interaction (UPI) and perceived credibility (PC) are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) and are therefore not supported in this study.

All significant relationships exhibit positive path coefficients, indicating that higher levels of IC, SE, and PU are associated with more favorable brand attitudes, which in turn lead to stronger purchase intentions. Among these, consumer brand attitude has the strongest effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.836$), highlighting its central role as a key determinant of consumer behavior.

Regarding the antecedents of brand attitude, scenario experience shows the strongest effect ($\beta = 0.287$), followed closely by perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.284$), and interesting content ($\beta = 0.215$). These findings suggest that experiential and cognitive factors play a more prominent role than purely hedonic elements in shaping brand evaluations in short-form video contexts.

To further assess the relative importance of predictors, effect size (f^2) was examined following the guidelines of Cohen (1988) and Chin (1998). The results indicate that perceived usefulness ($f^2 = 0.078$), scenario experience ($f^2 = 0.073$), and interesting content ($f^2 = 0.046$) have small but meaningful effects on brand attitude ($0.02 < f^2 < 0.15$). In contrast, user participation interaction and perceived credibility exhibit negligible effects ($f^2 < 0.02$), which is consistent with their non-significant path coefficients.

Notably, the effect size of consumer brand attitude on purchase intention is substantial ($f^2 = 2.315$), far exceeding the threshold of 0.35, indicating a large effect. This result reinforces the critical role of brand attitude as a key mechanism driving purchase intention.

The explanatory power of the model was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results show that consumer brand attitude explains 69.7% of the variance in purchase intention (adjusted $R^2 = 0.697$), indicating strong predictive power. Similarly, the independent variables (IC, SE, and PU) explain 70.5% of the variance in consumer brand attitude (adjusted $R^2 = 0.705$), suggesting that the model has substantial explanatory capability. The remaining variance may be attributed to other factors not included in the model as well as random error.

Overall, the results confirm the robustness of the proposed model and highlight the dominant role of brand attitude in mediating the relationship between short-form video attributes and purchase intention.

V. DISCUSSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1 Discussion

This study provides robust empirical evidence that short-form video attributes significantly influence consumers' purchase intention on the Shopee e-commerce platform through the mediating role of brand attitude. Specifically, scenario experience, perceived usefulness, and interesting content are found to have significant positive effects on consumer brand attitude, which in turn strongly drives purchase intention. Among these factors, scenario experience exerts the strongest influence on brand attitude ($\beta = 0.287$, $p < 0.001$), followed closely by perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.284$, $p < 0.001$), while interesting content shows a relatively weaker but still significant effect ($\beta = 0.215$, $p < 0.01$). These findings indicate that experiential and cognitive attributes of short-form video content are more influential than purely hedonic elements in shaping consumers' evaluative responses. In particular, the ability of video content to simulate real-life product usage contexts enhances immersion and perceived relevance, thereby strengthening brand evaluations. Furthermore, the results highlight the central role of consumer brand attitude as a key psychological mechanism within the integrated SOR-TPB framework. Brand attitude has a strong and significant impact on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.836$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that favorable brand evaluations are critical in converting consumer perceptions into behavioral intentions. This finding reinforces the role of brand attitude as a core mediator linking external stimuli (short-form video attributes) to behavioral responses (purchase intention).

The findings of this study are broadly consistent with prior research on short-form video marketing and consumer behavior, while also offering several noteworthy distinctions.

First, the positive impact of interesting content on brand attitude is aligned with the advertising value literature, which emphasizes the role of entertainment in shaping consumer responses (Ducoffe, 1996). This result is also consistent with recent empirical studies showing that engaging and creative video content enhances emotional responses and improves brand evaluations (Meng et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2025; Thao & Hai, 2024). However, the relatively lower effect size observed in this study suggests that, in the context of short-form video, entertainment alone may not be sufficient to strongly influence consumer attitudes, particularly when compared to more experience-driven factors.

Second, the strong influence of scenario experience on brand attitude confirms and extends previous findings in experiential marketing research. Prior studies have shown that immersive and scenario-based content enhances consumer participation interaction and emotional connection (Wu & Su, 2025; Meng et al., 2024; Thao & Hai, 2024). The current results reinforce this perspective by demonstrating that scenario experience is the most influential predictor of brand attitude in the Vietnamese e-commerce context. This highlights the importance of contextualized and relatable content in shaping consumer perceptions, especially in environments where physical product interaction is limited.

Third, the significant effect of perceived usefulness is consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) and subsequent research in online consumer behavior (Pavlou & Fygenon, 2006). The findings also align with recent studies indicating that informative and useful video content enhances decision-making efficiency and positively influences consumer attitudes (Liu & Wang, 2023). Notably, the relatively high impact of perceived usefulness in this study suggests that consumers in emerging markets place strong emphasis on functional and informational value when evaluating short-form video content.

In contrast, the non-significant effects of user participation interaction and perceived credibility diverge from several prior studies that highlight their importance in digital marketing contexts (Sun et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023). One possible explanation is that in short-form video environments characterized by rapid content consumption, superficial engagement behaviors (e.g., likes, shares) may not necessarily translate into deeper cognitive processing or attitude formation. Similarly, credibility cues may be less salient when consumers focus more on experiential and

informational aspects of content rather than source evaluation. These findings suggest that the role of engagement and credibility may be context-dependent and less influential in short-form, highly dynamic content environments.

Finally, the strong effect of consumer brand attitude on purchase intention is consistent with the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and a large body of empirical research in marketing (Spears & Singh, 2004; Thao & Hai, 2024). The magnitude of this relationship observed in the current study further confirms the central role of brand attitude as a key mediator in the SOR framework, linking external stimuli to behavioral outcomes.

Overall, while the findings largely support existing theoretical and empirical evidence, they also provide new insights by highlighting the dominant role of experiential and cognitive factors over interactive and credibility-related factors in short-form video marketing contexts.

5.2 Contributions

From a theoretical perspective, this study contributes to the literature in three key ways. First, it extends the SOR framework by demonstrating that experiential (scenario experience) and cognitive (perceived usefulness) stimuli are more influential than hedonic and interaction-based factors in short-form video contexts. Second, it integrates SOR with TPB to provide a clearer explanation of how internal psychological states (brand attitude) mediate the relationship between digital stimuli and behavioral outcomes. Third, it offers empirical evidence from an emerging market, highlighting the contextual differences in consumer behavior within e-commerce environments.

From a managerial perspective, the findings provide actionable insights for businesses, particularly in the slow-moving consumer goods sector such as sleep care products. Firms should prioritize scenario-based video content that reflects real-life usage contexts (e.g., sleep discomfort, environmental conditions), using narrative structures such as “before–during–after” to enhance relatability and emotional engagement.

Additionally, content should be designed to maximize perceived usefulness by delivering clear, structured, and actionable information, including product demonstrations, comparisons, and practical benefits. Sensory-rich techniques such as close-up shots, slow motion, and POV perspectives should be employed to simulate product experience effectively.

Moreover, incorporating authentic customer experiences and storytelling can strengthen emotional connection and reinforce brand attitude. Rather than focusing solely on entertainment, firms should balance experiential appeal with informational value to optimize effectiveness.

Overall, the findings suggest that short-form video marketing is not merely a communication tool but a strategic mechanism for shaping consumer perceptions and driving purchase behavior. Leveraging this format effectively can help firms enhance competitive advantage and adapt to the rapidly evolving digital commerce landscape.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigates the impact of short-form video attributes on consumers’ purchase intention on the Shopee e-commerce platform, with a particular focus on the mediating role of brand attitude. Drawing on the integrated Stimulus–Organism–Response (SOR) framework and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the findings provide strong empirical support for the proposed model. The results demonstrate that scenario experience, perceived usefulness, and interesting content significantly influence consumer brand attitude, which in turn has a substantial effect on purchase intention. Among these factors, scenario experience emerges as the most influential predictor, highlighting the importance of immersive and context-based content in shaping consumer evaluations. Additionally, perceived usefulness plays a critical role in enhancing consumers’ cognitive processing and reducing uncertainty in online decision-making. In contrast, user participation interaction and perceived credibility are found to have no significant effects, suggesting that their influence may be limited in fast-paced short-form video environments. Importantly, the study confirms the central role of brand attitude as a key mediating mechanism that translates external stimuli into behavioral intention. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how short-form video marketing functions within digital commerce contexts, particularly in emerging markets. Overall, the study underscores that effective short-form video strategies should prioritize experiential realism and informational value to influence consumer attitudes and drive purchase intention in increasingly competitive e-commerce environments.

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. First, the use of non-probability sampling in a single-country context (Vietnam) may limit generalizability; future research should employ probability sampling and cross-country designs. Second, the focus on one platform (Shopee) and a specific product category restricts applicability; broader contexts should be examined. Third, the cross-sectional design limits temporal insights; longitudinal studies are recommended. Finally, future research could incorporate additional variables (e.g., trust, perceived risk) and test moderating effects such as demographics or digital literacy.

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